

Institute of **Physics**

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**The Environmental
Physics Group**

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Editor's Report

This is my last Bulletin of the Environmental Physics Group, as I have resigned from the EPG Committee and from this position as Editor. The work that I *must* do has expanded to such an extent that I am forced to cut down on voluntary work.

I want to thank my fellow committee members for the support they have given me as Editor of this newsletter. They were especially tolerant when this edition became more and more overdue — and I apologise to the readers for being so late.

As this is my last editorial, I will indulge in a brief ramble about the EPG. It seems to me that the environmental sciences are going to assume a central position in human endeavour. Thus I expect the Environmental Physics Group to expand and become increasingly vigorous over the next few years. Committee work is an essential component of the process and promotion of science. It can be exciting and challenging, and it can be mundane or even boring — sometimes all of these within a single meeting! For me, it has been both a duty and a pleasure to serve the science community for several years.

If you think you have something to offer the Environmental Physics Group, please contact one of the committee members (see the back page for contacts).

*David Pearson
University of Reading*

Chairman's Report 1998

For the last three years we have held our annual general meeting at the Physics Congress where we have staged a one-day meeting on an environmental physics topic. The poor attendance last year, when we discussed environmental modelling, prompted a change to hold this year's AGM in London and to join with the London and Southeast Branch for a talk by Jon Shanklin from the British Antarctic Survey. Next year we are considering holding the AGM as part of a "Member's Day" at which we will invite members to relate their work as environmental physicists.

Although we have more than five hundred members in the Group, poor attendance has been a worrying feature at all the events that the Committee has organised this year. We have held two half-day meetings at the Institute. The first was on "Light extinction in the atmosphere: a problem for environmentalists and astronomers". We thank Dr. McNally, who retired recently as the Director of the London Observatory, for suggesting this meeting and for organising the programme. The second was on

"Environmental noise" and was held jointly with the Institute of Acoustics. Both these meetings were excellent and deserved much larger attendances. The Group also co-sponsored the Second International Conference on Urban Air Quality, held in Madrid in March. Some members of the Group enjoyed visits to the Silsoe Research Institute in June and to Imperial College's field centre at Silwood Park in September.

The Education Group under the chairmanship of Peter Hughes has again been active. A summer school was held at the University of Exeter in July. We had hoped for at least fifteen teachers to attend this event, but only six registered. In spite of this low number, those that attended enjoyed a series of talks on environmental physics and on how environmental physics might be integrated into the school curriculum. The textbook on environmental physics, prepared for schools teaching environmental physics as an examination subject and edited by Nigel Mason and Peter Hughes, should be published by the end of the year.

In July the Group is co-sponsoring a meeting on Optical Oceanography and UV Radiation during the 22nd General Assembly of the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics at the University of Birmingham. At the British Association meeting in Sheffield in September there will be a session on "Global environmental change", which has been arranged through the EPG Committee. We hope also to arrange various visits to places of interest. The Environmental Physics Group now has their own page on the Institute of Physics Web site and this provides a calendar of events.

Finally, I have to acknowledge and thank on your behalf the work of members of the committee, especially the conscientious work of our secretary, Peter Hodgson. Also we must thank David Pearson who has been the editor of the EPG Bulletin and is now retiring from this position. Many members have served on the Committee in one capacity or other since the inception of the Group and are now standing down. We look forward to having new committee members which should ensure a good future for the Group.

E.G. Youngs

New Committee Profile

Welcome to three new committee members: Dr. Sian Bethan of Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants; Dr. Derek Rose of the University of Newcastle upon Tyne; and Dr. Barbara Gabrys of the University of Oxford. Dr. Rose will take over as editor of this Bulletin, and Dr. Gabrys will be in charge of the Group's Web pages.

Visit report: Silwood Park, 21 October 1998.

Silwood park is a laboratory of Imperial College in the grounds of the former country house of the same name one or two miles to the east of Ascot. Eight members of the Environmental Physics Group enjoyed an interesting day with a varied programme of environmental studies. David Brassington showed an ingenious technique for the *in situ* measurement of common pollutant gases at ppb levels in the atmosphere, using a tuneable diode laser. We also saw delayed neutron activation analysis, used for the very rapid and economical determination of uranium in soil and other environmental samples, described by Roger Benzeng. After a pleasant lunch in the cafeteria the group visited the wind tunnel facility used by Rob Kinnersley and several of his colleagues to study the deposition of contaminants from the atmosphere onto plants. In addition to dry deposition of particles this facility has been used in conjunction with a rain simulator to investigate the effect of rain in removing pollutants and the contamination of crop surfaces by wet deposition. Finally, Brian Bennett showed us the nuclear reactor which plays important part in the environmental programme through the irradiation of samples, enabling highly sensitive analysis for many tracers by neutron activation analysis.

The participants found the whole day most rewarding and warmly thanked Rob Kinnersley for setting up and hosting the visit.

E.G. Youngs

Report on The First Institute of Physics Environmental Physics Summer School, Exeter University, 11–12 July 1998.

Radioactivity dispersion
10 days after the
Chernobyl nuclear
accident (Hollander and
Petersen, 1995)

Sponsored by:

The Institute of Physics
The Environmental Physics Group
The Natural Environment Research Council
The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council

Several "A" examination boards now include aspects of Environmental Physics in their programmes, and many universities now include at least one module of Environmental Physics in their programmes. The aim of the Summer School was to illustrate the scope and breadth of this interdisciplinary subject, to "A" level teachers and university lecturers, through presentations, demonstrations and a visit to the Earth Resources Centre at Exeter University. Hopefully, aspects of the subject will then be incorporated into future curriculum development and their teaching.

I would like to express our gratitude to our sponsors (the Institute of Physics and the Environmental Physics Group, the Natural Environment Research Council and the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council), and the presenters (please see below), Mrs. Catherine Wilson M.B.E. and the staff of the IoP's Education Department for their energy and enthusiasm, and Professor Adrian Wyatt and Dr. Bill Vennart (Physics Department, Exeter University) for preparing the ground. The NERC also stipulated:

"We do not often give such sponsorship, but as the aims of your initiative coincide closely with one of the NERC's current objectives we are keen to help. NERC recognises that innovation in the environmental sciences often occurs at interfaces between disciplines. The environmental sciences need to attract first-rate physicists, mathematicians, engineers, chemists and computer scientists. We feel that your summer school will assist in this matter."

I would also like to thank the staff at the Crossmeads Conference Centre, Exeter, for the excellent accommodation, meals and facilities.

The presentations

The Biosphere : the Soil-Plant-Atmosphere Continuum Professor Edward Youngs (Cranfield University)

Growing plants need a supply of energy and water for their survival. The system for the transfer of energy and water through plants between the atmosphere and the soil is referred to as the "soil-plant-atmosphere continuum" (SPAC). The energy is supplied mainly by solar short-wave radiation and used mainly as latent heat in the phase change of liquid water to vapour. Other energy sources and sinks are associated with respiration and photosynthesis. Other components in the energy balance include long-wave radiation, sensible heat transfer in air and soil, and changes in the sensible heat content of the SPAC. Water is supplied from water stored in the soil and through precipitation, and lost by evaporation from plants and the soil surface together with some through soil water redistribution. Except during precipitation and the rare occurrences of condensation and sublimation, the direction of water transfer is from

the soil to the atmosphere. Water movement in the soil is by viscous flow in the liquid phase and by diffusion in the gaseous phase. The process of water movement in plants is in the liquid phase, either as diffusion across membranes or as viscous flow in conducting vessels. The transfer into the atmospheric boundary layer in contact with bare soil and plant leaves is by molecular diffusion of vapour. In the natural atmosphere the transfer of water vapour is almost entirely by turbulent diffusion.

Water moves in the SPAC as a result of differences in water potential with each component in the system providing a resistance to the water flow. In unsaturated soil, water is held in lenses between soil particles, giving rise to a matric potential on account of surface tension forces across the curved menisci. The total water potential is the sum of the gravitational potential, the matric potential and the osmotic potential due to any salts in the soil solution. The water in the plants has a high osmotic potential that is opposed by the turgor potential arising from the resistance to the expansion of the strong cellulose cell walls. The plant wilts if the turgor potential is reduced to zero due to the lack of water. Water movement into the plant is via the semi-permeable root cells, driven by the difference in total water potential across the roots. Water moves out of the plant mainly from the stomata of plant leaves. The water vapour density in contact with the stomata can be equated to a potential by means of a thermodynamic relation. Thus, the water movement through the plants via the xylem cells is driven by the difference in water potential at the stomata and the root. Outside the plant, gradients of soil-water potential deliver water to the plant roots while gradients of water vapour density, equivalent to gradients of water potential, transfer the water away from the plants into the atmosphere.

The Physics of Air Pollution and Environmental Health

Professor Ron Hamilton (University of Middlesex)

The study of air pollution requires the scientific understanding of a range of processes and interactions which together are responsible for the concentration to which humans and ecosystems are exposed and the consequences of their exposure.

The main contributions made by physics and physicists have been:

1. Modelling (e.g. the use of Gaussian-based predictive models and wind tunnel models),
2. Monitoring (e.g. electron microscopy for particle analysis and light scattering for particle size analysis), and
3. IT systems for communication.

Satellite Remote Sensing

Dr. Craig Underwood (University of Surrey)

The aim of this presentation is to show some of the educational opportunities offered to teach science through the use of Earth observation satellite data. We shall make use of the resource materials (slides, books, CD-ROMs, etc) which are currently available, and discuss practical work which can be done in this area, including the live reception of satellite image data.

The emphasis of the presentation will be on developing a course which will enable students to attain an understanding of the physical principles involved in remote sensing (i.e. orbits, the electromagnetic spectrum, propagation, sensors, optics, and resolution), and in the process make students aware of the important role of the physicist in environmental monitoring.

We shall review the major Earth observation satellites (e.g. NOAA, METEOSAT, GOES, NIMBUS, METEOR, LANDSAT, SPOT, and ERS), and look at the application of their data to atmospheric physics, meteorology, climatology, oceanography, Earth resources and land-use surveying.

The Atmosphere: Climate and Climate Change

Dr. Nigel Mason (University College London)

Throughout the Earth's history, major fluctuations in climate have been caused by many factors: volcanic eruptions that obscure the Sun, the impact of meteorites, the changing positions of the landmasses caused by continental drift, changes in the Earth's orbit around the Sun and the periodicity of the Solar activity. Some periods of change, such as the ice ages, when the general climate was 10-12°C colder than at present, continued for thousands of years while smaller variations, such as the 'little ice age' lasted from the 15th to the 19th century, when rivers froze regularly in the colder winters — the last Thames 'frost fair' being held in 1814.

Today we face the possibility of global climate change occurring not only through such natural cycles but also through our own modification of atmospheric processes arising from our increased industrialisation of the planet. The last decade has seen large fluctuations in the climate across the Earth, increased storms in the Americas, increased droughts in Africa, and longer and warmer summers in Europe. Are these evidence of induced 'global warming' arising from increased industrial emissions, or are they part of a natural cycle? If we are changing the Earth's climate what are the likely consequences for agriculture, population growth and standards of living? What can be done to control such effects?

This talk will discuss both the evidence for changes in the Earth's climate due to increased global industrialisation and its consequences for both governments and individuals.

Environmental Physics in the Field : Earthwatch Millennium Fellowships

Mr. Peter Hughes (Kingsway College London)

This illustrated talk will discuss the potentialities for Environmental Physics in the field, with emphasis on the Earthwatch Millennium Fellowships. Starting with examples of Environmental Physics in the laboratory, such as the simulation of renewable energy sources, reference will then be made to the types of Environmental Physics which can be deployed in the field. These will include weather stations that can be used in schools and the scope for air pollution monitoring.

Earthwatch Millennium Fellowships provide a marvellous context in which Environmental Physics in the field can be experienced by teachers and post-16 students alike. Reference will be made to the Baltic Glaciers Geophysics Project. This entailed the collection of the evidence of the direction and magnitude of energy flows and the sedimentological deposition of sands, gravels, stones and boulders in gravel pits in central Sweden and in the Stockholm Archipelago. This evidence will be analysed with the aim of reconstructing the climate change that accompanied the recession of the last Scandinavian ice-sheet 10,000 years ago.

Renewable Energy: Some Thoughts

Professor Roger Wootton (City University)

It is clear to everyone that there will be increasing interest in the use of renewable energy rather than fossil fuels over the career span of today's schoolchildren. What is less obvious is that this change in emphasis will require a lot more technical effort, a lot more use of physics, technology, and engineering than getting the same amount of energy from geological energy sources.

This talk explains the major opportunities for renewable energy such as wind, solar, wave, tidal, energy crop and geothermal for the UK and their use in electrical supply at national and local level as well as the issues related to transport energy. The economic exploitation of each requires development of many areas of Physics. The talk discusses how expansion of renewable energy will need the whole population to have a little relevant knowledge as well as specially educated professionals. The challenge is enormous.

Finally, there will be a few words on the controversial issue of the role of nuclear energy: a physicist's dream that has gone wrong, or is it only just beginning?

Environmental Change in Antarctica

Dr. Jonathan Shanklin (British Antarctic Survey)

This presentation focuses on two global environmental issues, which are of particular significance in Antarctica.

The British Antarctic Survey is responsible for implementing British policy in the Antarctic. Run from its Cambridge headquarters, it has two year-round Antarctic stations, two summer-only stations, numerous field camps and runs two ships and five aircraft. The scientific studies cover all aspects of research in the Antarctic, ranging

from earth sciences (mapping, geology, geophysics), ice and climate studies (meteorology, glaciology, chemistry), life sciences (marine, terrestrial and human) to upper atmospheric physics. Scientists may visit the Antarctic for a short summer stay, or spend up to two years collecting data. In addition to the scientists, support staff are required to maintain the smooth day to day running of the stations.

Two global environmental issues are associated with the Antarctic: global warming and the ozone hole. The popular perception is that the polar ice caps are melting and that low-lying areas around the globe will be flooded. The truth is rather different. Antarctic ice-cores tell us what our past climate has been like, and give us clues to what may happen in the future. The changes to the ice-shelves that we are seeing at present may be part of a natural cycle of climate change in the Antarctic, but global warming will affect the continent in the future.

The Antarctic ozone hole was discovered by British Antarctic Survey scientists and is a graphic demonstration of how easy it is to change our atmosphere. I will explain why the ozone hole forms over Antarctica and the precautions that we need to take. There is often confusion between the ozone hole and global warming, but there are links between them. Recent studies suggest that within the next 15 years an ozone hole could form over the Arctic and affect the UK.

Meteorology and the Internet

Dr. Roger Brugge (University of Reading)

Participants will be provided with hands-on experience of using a World Wide Web browser. Examples of how to use the browser and the WWW to search for information of meteorological and environmental interest will be given. Participants will be encouraged to search for information pertaining to their own requirements, and use will be made of the tutor's homepage at <http://www.met.rdg.ac.uk/~brugge>.

Environmental Applications of LASER Photonics and Robotics : You Can Achieve Anything — with a LASER

Mr. Ray Davies (University of Salford)

Photonics has been identified as the technology for the 21st century, and Environmental Physics presents one of the most important study areas that will influence us all during the 21st century. Using low-power LASER diodes, and HeNe LASERS, a series of working LASER Application Projects, that have been designed and constructed very recently, will serve to illustrate some of the many uses to which Photonics can be assigned within the student laboratory situation.

The tremendously attractive visual appeal of LASER based projects will be used to illustrate some of the novel designs that can be developed in any student laboratory for earthquake detection, ocean floor spreading sensing, terrestrial remote sensing, communication links, smart structures within the environment, LASER simulation, and many other key parameters from within Environmental Physics. This Workshop will also demonstrate a highly innovative approach to the use of working LASER Guided Mobile Robots for operation in hazardous environmental situations, such as in underwater investigations, or in sampling from volcanic areas, or in space, where

radio control communication may well be ineffective.

This Workshop will emphasise that the interaction of photons with the environment yields valuable information, as well as a great appeal for both students and tutors.

Visit to the Earth Resources Centre Exeter University

This was a marvellous experience. Both Dr. Peter Grainger (Director) and Dr. John Merefield (Deputy-Director) showed us around the Centre where we saw its work, which focuses on environmental monitoring, protection and management. It is engaged in consultancy and research into air and water quality monitoring, hydrogeology, environmental analysis, microscopy, environmental radioactivity, waste disposal and engineering geology.

Both the presenters and the delegates found the weekend exciting, productive, and very informative. The presentations were visually stunning and the demonstrations by Ray Davies and Roger Brugge provided a mine of ideas for experimentation and the use of IT respectively in developing Environmental Physics.

Peter Hughes
Chair,
IOP Environmental Physics Group's
Education Sub-Committee

Spread the Good News!

The continued vigour of our Group will be ensured by a flow of new members. A leaflet is available from the Institute or from members of your committee to publicise the Environmental Physics Group. Why not hand a few to colleagues, or take a handful to any suitable meetings?

To request a supply please speak or write to any committee member or to Leah Goldson, Institute of Physics, 76 Portland Place, London W1N 3DH. Tel. (0171) 470 4800, email leah.goldson@iop.org

Meeting Report — “Optical Extinction in the Atmosphere: a Problem for Environmentalists and Astronomers”. February, 3 1999, Institute of Physics, London.

The meeting opened with an account by Dr. D. McNally (University of London Observatory) of the increasing problem faced by astronomers from light pollution — the upward escape of outdoor lighting. The escaping light is scattered by particulates and this is further added to by downward scatter from the lower inversion layers so that at any given site, the level of light pollution derives both from local sources of illumination and distant sources. While it is clearly advantageous to reduce the source of the illumination by good luminaire design, it is also desirable to reduce the source of the scatterers. He also drew attention to astronomical concerns on global warming in regard to increased cloudiness. While one could clearly point to occasions when aircraft contrails spread out to form high thin cloud detrimental to astronomical observation, there was a certain amount of anecdotal (*not* evidential) suggestion that in temperate regions cloudiness may be becoming more common. The effects of increasing concentrations of heavy molecules in the stratosphere on infrared astronomy were also outlined.

Professor K. Shine (University of Reading) discussed the changes occurring in the molecular composition of the atmosphere — the increase of CO₂ and other greenhouse molecules. He briefly discussed the seasonal “polar” decreases in stratospheric O₃. O₃ was also becoming a serious lower atmosphere pollutant. He drew attention to the growing concentrations of non-methane hydrocarbons in urban situations. Such gases, for example acetylene, are serious contributors to greenhouse effects. The rôle of CFCs as greenhouse gases was also addressed and he noted that CFC replacement by HCFCs presented non-trivial problems in assessing their contribution to atmospheric degradation — the mix of IR absorbers in the atmosphere, and their rôle in its energy balance, are changing rapidly and are inhomogeneous. He was reassuring that the accumulation of heavy molecules in the stratosphere was now beginning to show a downturn.

Dr. R. Colville (ICSTM) discussed the relationship of atmospheric particulates in relation to public health. While naturally occurring particulates such as sulphates and NaCl crystals were well studied, the range of urban particulates, e.g. diesel soot, was more varied. The urban particulates tended to occur in a bimodal size distribution, with peaks at 10 nm and 100 nm. The standards for particle characterisation were set up in relation to public health concerns, and there was now some question of the analytical value of these standards. Nevertheless the standards as now existing were exceeded in most UK cities, one day in 10 currently. This is not a good situation, given that atmospheric particulates may play active rôles in disease transmission as well as more well known aspects of public health.

The afternoon was concluded by Dr. G. Hayman (AEA) who discussed the transmission of ultra-violet radiation in the atmosphere. While stratospheric O₃ absorbed UVC radiation (200–280 nm), UVB (280–320 nm) and UVA (320–400 nm) could reach ground level, though attenuated by absorption in the atmosphere. While there was considerable public concern about increase in the numbers of skin cancers, there was need for considerable research on biological responses to variation of radiation wavelength. He noted that while Antarctic Ozone amounts could drop by 60%, the drop in the Arctic was more usually 20–35% (though a drop by 45% had been experienced in Canada in March 1998); in New Zealand levels of UV radiation reaching ground levels were a factor of two greater than in the UK. These interesting statistics could not be pushed too hard as a basis for remedial action: the situation was a complex one in which desirable changes in the concentrations of one pollutant could increase other hazards, e.g. since the UK Clean Air Acts there had been a 27% increase in rural, and a 52% increase in urban, areas in UV radiation at ground level. The very clear message was that considerable study and care in interpretation was needed before pollution problems could be tackled successfully.

This was a meeting of very great interest bringing together a very wide range of topics which were impacted by the phenomenon of atmospheric pollution — from human health to meteorological changes and the deterioration of astronomical observational conditions at optical and infrared wavelengths. The overall view that emerged was that the consequences of atmospheric pollution were highly complex, coupled and far from fully understood. The example of attempting to decrease one type of pollution with effects on another hazard left a moral problem for consideration in our efforts to beneficially reduce atmospheric pollution.

D. McNally
University of London Observatory

Ph.D. Abstract

Concentrations and vertical profiles of airborne particulate matter

Alfred Micallef, November 1998, University of Nottingham.

Supervised by: Dr. Jeremy J. Colls, University of Nottingham.

The main objective of the thesis was to measure and model concentrations and vertical profiles of airborne particulate matter over the first three metres from ground.

For measurement purpose an electronically-controlled sequential sampling system, based on the lift design, has been developed to sample air at six levels over a height range of 3 m. The mass concentration of various fractions of airborne particulate matter was measured near real-time using a portable optical particle monitor (Model 1.104/5, Grimm Labortechnik Ltd., Ainring, Germany). Sampling was mainly carried out in an urban street canyon in Loughborough, Leicestershire; but some measurements were also carried out in a rural area on the outskirts of Loughborough, and indoors (coffee room, electronics workshop, undergraduate student hostel and library) for comparison. The measured concentration gradients were not negligible, especially in confined environments and for large particle size ranges, and have implications on human exposure of groups breathing at different heights and on siting of air pollution monitoring systems.

The other aspect of the work relates to modelling of concentrations and vertical profiles of airborne particulate matter. Only the urban street canyon was considered. The net result was a Street Level Air Quality (SLAQ) model which is a practical emission-dispersion model for the prediction of vehicle-derived total suspended particulate matter (SPM), PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentration for receptors within the confines of the street. The model was evaluated by fixed-point monitoring in a street canyon and then used to model vertical concentration profiles within the boundary layer of the canyon. Modelled and measured vertical concentration profiles were compared as means for further spatial and temporal evaluation of the air quality model. Despite problems with the measurement technique, sampling methodology and modelling, agreement between modelled and measured data was reasonably good with correlation coefficients in the range 0.62–0.82.

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Meetings, Conferences and Events

EURESCO CONFERENCES

Information taken from the ESF WWW site
www.esf.org/euresco/erc_call/erc_call.htm

“Since 1990 the European Science Foundation (ESF) has been running the Programme of European Research Conferences (EURESCO), consisting of top-level scientific discussion meetings in all areas of research, from mathematics and natural sciences to engineering sciences, social sciences and humanities. This Programme promotes series of meetings, devoted to the same general subject, normally taking place about every other year. In the past, most conferences have been supported by the European Commission, on a case by case basis, as Euroconferences. Close to 300 conferences have been organised by EURESCO up to the end of 1998.

The European Science Foundation has decided to give a new impetus to the EURESCO scheme to continue the development of a high standard European Conference Programme which will set up a world-wide reference. Increased financial backing from the Foundation's member organisations combined with the ongoing support of the European Commission will allow ESF to strengthen the EURESCO scheme in the years ahead. The objective is to increase the number of conferences organised annually to between 40 and 50. The ESF is now inviting proposals for new conference series, as well as for the continuation of established ones, when justified.

The following scheme is now being implemented:

Following peer review, the EURESCO Committee will draw up a shortlist of high quality conference proposals. Proposals fitting into priority areas of the Fifth Framework Programme will be submitted, with the administrative support of ESF, to the European Commission for a Euroconference grant. For each EC-supported conference ESF will then provide additional funding of up to 10000 euros. For shortlisted conferences that do not receive EC support ESF will provide grants of up to 25000 euros. In both cases, Conference Chairpersons will be strongly encouraged to seek co-sponsoring from alternative sources (industry, trusts and foundations, various national sources...).

The deadline for the present Call for Proposals is 15 September 1999. Only proposals for conferences taking place in the year 2001 or after will be considered. About 30 proposals are likely to be selected for funding.”

See the Web site for details on how to apply.

Soil and Water Conservation Society Annual Conference. 8–11 August 1999, Biloxi, Mississippi.

Pat Mulligan, Conference Manager. Tel. +1 515 289 2331, email patm@swcs.org, www.swcs.org

Abstract deadline has passed.

The World's Natural Forests and their Rôle in Global Processes. 15–20 August 1999, Khabarovsk, Russia.

Victor Grek, FEFRI, 71 Volochaevskaya Street, 680030 Khabarovsk, Russia. Tel. +7 4212 217952, fax +7 4212 216798, email sergey@nilkh.khabarovsk.su

Second International Conference On Re-Analyses. 23–27 August 1999, Wokefield Park, Mortimer, Reading, UK.

See <http://www.ecmwf.int/> or contact Dr. D. Burridge, ECMWF, Shinfield Park, Reading, RG2 9AX, UK. Telephone: 0118 949 9000, fax: 0118 986 9450 Email: reanalyses2@ecmwf.int

Third International Symposium on Environmental Software Systems. 30 August–2 September 1999, University of Otago, Dunedin, New Zealand.

“The purpose of the symposium is to present and discuss the fundamentals, progress and actual trends in this area in terms of methods, tools and state-of-the-art applications.”

Topics include the following applications and methods:

- Monitoring
- Measurement networks
- Waste management
- Knowledge bases
- Water resource management
- GIS, inventories
- Administrative systems
- Information systems

- Impact assessment
- Decision support
- Ecosystem research
- Modelling, Visualisation
- Agriculture
- Remote sensing
- Ecological management
- Ecobalances
- Environmental networks
- Distributed technology
- Process control
- Real time systems

See <http://isess.crlle.uoguelph.ca/1999-scope.html>

Deadline for abstracts has passed.

ECODRIVE — Green transport for a cleaner environment. 16–17 September 1999, Graz, Austria.

“The conference will consider how driving in an energy efficient manner can be achieved without complicated or costly measures. It will take the approach of an international conference and a national workshop. Representatives from the Austrian Ministry for Science and Transport and the Ministry for Environment, Youth and Family will open the event, along with Patrick Lambert, representing the European Commission’s Energy Directorate General (DG XVII) and Karl-Heinz Posch, from Austrian Mobility Research.”

Registration deadline: 14 September 1999.

Austrian Mobility Research: Petra Mautner. Tel. +43 316 81045119; fax +43 316 81045175, email: mautner@fgm-amor.at

Horizontal Well Drilling: The New Dimension. 21–22 September 1999, Baltimore, Maryland.

A. Stone, Executive Director, American Groundwater Trust, 16 Center Street, Concord, NH 03301, USA. Tel. +1 603 228 5444, fax +1 602 228 6557, email agwt@aol.com, <http://www.agwt.org>

Science-Technology Synergy for Research in Marine Environment: Challenges for the 21st Century. 8–15 September 1999, Erice, Sicily.

P. Favali, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica, Via di Vigna Murata 605, Roma, Italy 00143. Tel. +39 6 51860341, fax +39 6 51860338, email geostar@ing750.ingrm.it

Seventh International Conference on Salt Lakes. 12–15 September 1999, Death Valley, California.

J. Melack, Donald Bren School of Environmental Science and Management, University of California, Santa Barbara, CA 93106, USA. Tel. +1 805 893 3879, fax +1 805 893 4724, email melack@lifesci.ucsb.edu.

Abstracts deadline: 1 August 1999.

Second International Workshop on Multiangular Measurements and Models (IWMMM-2). Ispra, Italy, 15–17 September 1999.

“This Workshop is organised by the Space Applications Institute (SAI) of the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC), and sponsored by the ENAMORS network. The Workshop will focus on techniques and applications of directional and spectral measurements acquired in the laboratory and field, as well as from airborne and spaceborne campaigns. Special sessions will be organised to address three special themes, namely the simulation of the directional reflectance of the radiatively coupled surface-atmosphere system, recent progress in the measurement of anisotropic targets, and the exploitation of multiangular measurements and models in practical applications. This meeting will thus permit to review the progress made in modelling, instrumentation and applications since the first IWMMM, which was held in Beijing in September 1996.”

Detailed information can be found at <http://www.enamors.org/>

The IWMMM-2 will precede the **International Workshop on Satellite Remote Sensing and Climate Simulations: Synergies and Limitations**, that will take place in **Les Diablerets, Switzerland, September 20–24, 1999**. This latter conference, organised jointly by the Department of Geography of the University of Fribourg and the Space Applications Institute, will address the broader theme of “Remote Sensing and Global Climate Change”, and will provide a forum to discuss the role of Earth Observation from space in addressing global climate and environmental change issues, in particular from the point of view of improving regional and global simulations. Special sessions will be organised to address three special themes, namely the observation and parameterisation of land surface processes, the characterisation and representation of atmospheric aerosols, and scaling/nesting issues. More information on the purpose and venue of that event is posted under the University of Fribourg Web site, <http://www.unifr.ch/iguf/EVENTS/diable.htm> which is also reachable from the ENAMORS address indicated above.

EOS/SPIE Symposium on Remote Sensing, including conferences on Atmospheric Sensing, Earth Surface Sensing and Platforms and Systems. 20–24 September 1999, University of Florence, Italy.

See <http://www.europto.org/>

Society of Organic Petrology (TSOP) 16th Annual Meeting. 26–28 September 1999, Salt Lake City, Utah.

J. Quick, Utah Geological Survey, 1594 West North Temple, Suite 3110, Salt Lake City, UT 84114-6100, USA. Tel. +1 801 537 3372, fax +1 801 537 3400, email nrugs.jquick@state.ut.us, <http://www.tsop.org/>

Abstract deadline has passed.

The Earth Technologies Forum. 27–29 September 1999, Washington DC.

Conference Office, 2111 Wilson Blvd., Arlington, VA 22201, USA. Tel. +1 703 807 4052, fax +1 703 243 2874, email earthforum@alcalde-fay.com, WWW <http://www.earthforum.com/>

Second World Manufacturing Congress (WMC'99). September 27–30, 1999 at Durham University, U.K.

Purpose of the Congress: Manufacturing for the Millennium.

“The emphasis of this congress is on bringing researchers and industry closer together and endeavour to highlight the importance of both theoretical and applied research in the light of new shifts in the global economy. The continuous exchange of scientific and technical information is of particular importance in a time of world-wide challenges in the manufacturing industry. The impact of other rapidly changing industries such as microelectronics, automation, computer/information engineering and environmental protection is evolving new philosophies in manufacturing. The congress, to be held every second year, is meant to be a forum for academia and industry for research and the transfer of research to practice. The previous congress held in New Zealand (WMC'97) attracted participants from 35 countries around the world.”

The following symposia form part of WMC'99:

- ISMS'99 International Symposium on Manufacturing Systems
- ISMT'99 International Symposium on Manufacturing Technology

- ISMM'99 International Symposium on Manufacturing Management

ICSC International Computer Science Conventions, P.O. Box 279, Millet AB T0C 1Z0, Canada. Email operating@icsc.ab.ca. Fax +1-780-387-4329. Phone +1-780-387-3546

or

Dr. Mozafar Saadat, General Chair WMC'99, School of Engineering and Advanced Technology, University of Sunderland, Edinburgh Building, Chester Road, Sunderland SR1 3SD, U.K. Email mozafar.saadat@sunderland.ac.uk, Fax 0191-515-2703, Phone 0191-515-2867.

See also <http://www.icsc.ab.ca/wmc99.htm>

The deadline for submissions has passed.

Symposium: The impact of pollution on the Mediterranean. 2–6 October 1999, Alicante, Spain.

“The Mediterranean Scientific Association for Environmental Protection (MESAEP) has released a second announcement and call for papers for the tenth international symposium on environmental pollution and its impact on the Mediterranean region. The event is scheduled to take place in Alicante, Spain, from 2 to 6 October 1999.

The event aims to provide a forum in which scientists can share their results and discuss the current technological and legal measures to avoid or reduce pollution in the Mediterranean Sea. Conference participants will have the opportunity to put suggestions and recommendations to the regulatory authorities on environmental quality and safety in the Mediterranean and its neighbouring countries.”

MESAEP e.V. PO Box 460524 D-80913 Munich.
Email: mesaep@gsf.de <http://www.gsf.de/mesaep/>

European Geophysical Society Plinius Conference on Mediterranean Storms. 14–16 October 1999, Maratea, Italy.

EGS Office, Max-Planck-Straße 13, 37191 Katlenburg-Lindau, Germany. Tel. +49 5556 1440, fax +49 5556 4709, email egs@copernicus.org, <http://www.copernicus.org/EGS/conference/plc1/cover.htm>

Deadline for abstracts has passed.

International Conference On Environmental Modelling And Simulation. 23–27 January 2000, San Diego, California.

“The SCS (The Society for Computer Simulation International) Environment 2000 conference provides a forum for the exchange of concepts, methods and technologies among scientists committed to the modelling and simulation of the environment. The goal of the conference is to promote the applications of computer based models and simulations to a fully international constituency, as the prime tool for use in planning, implementing and monitoring a sustainable future for the environment.

The conference will focus on the modelling and simulation of various components of the environmental systems in different scales (as in atmosphere and oceans, hydrological processes, biochemical and biological cycles, air quality, impacts of human activities, and socioeconomic impacts). An additional emphasis will be on the applications of information technologies in visualisations and gathering/distribution of simulation results and observations to an international constituency.

Environment researchers, simulations modellers, GIS/remote sensing experts, and visualisation specialists are encouraged to submit papers in, but not limited to, the following topics:

- Modelling and Simulation Techniques including Numerical Aspects, Software Implementation and Visualisation Tools
- Decision Support Systems
- Climate Modelling
- Global Pollution and Global Climate Change
- Pollution: Air, Water, Soil, Noise, Radiation
- Air Quality Management
- Transboundary Air Pollution Modelling
- Traffic and Emission Modelling
- Ground Water, Surface Water, and Watershed Modelling
- Biochemical and Biological Modelling
- Biological Systems (Population Systems, Growth Models)
- Environmental Accidents and Risk Management
- Environmental Systems: Meteorology, Micrometeorology, Hydrology
- Economy-Energy Modelling
- Sustainable Development and Integrated Assessment Modelling
- Socioeconomic-environmental Impacts
- Remote Sensing, Satellite Data and Image Processing (Applications in Environmental Modelling)
- Geographic Information Systems (Applications in Environmental Modelling)”

Dr. Achim Sydow, Research Institute for Computer Architecture & Software Techniques. Tel. +49 30 6392-1813, email: sydow@first.gmd.de

Short abstracts due: August 31 1999
Notification of paper acceptance September 15 1999
Camera-ready paper due to SCS October 31 1999

American Geophysical Union Ocean Sciences Meeting. 24–28 January 2000, San Antonio, Texas.

A large and eclectic conference. Contact AGU Meetings Department, 2000 Florida Avenue NW, Washington, DC 20009, USA. Tel. +1 800 996 2481 or +1 202 462 6900, fax +1 202 328 0566, email meetinginfo@agu.org (use subject “2000 Ocean Sciences Meeting”), <http://www.agu.org>

Deadline for abstracts by post: 23 September 1999
Deadline for abstracts by WWW: 30 September 1999

7th International Symposium on Smart Structures and Materials. 5–9 March 2000, Newport Beach, California.

SPiE, PO Box 10, Bellingham, WA 98227, USA. Tel. +1 360 676 3290, fax +1 360 647 1445, email spie@spie.org, <http://www.spie.org/info/ss-nde>

Abstracts deadline: 9 August 1999.

“Information for Sustainable Development” — 28th International Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment and 3rd Symposium of the African Association of Remote Sensing of the Environment. 27–31 March 2000, Cape Town, South Africa.

“This symposium will bring together experts in one of the Earth’s key sciences on the most southern tip of Africa — representing a concentration of knowledge and experience in remote sensing of the environment.”

The 28th ISRSE Technical Committee, PO Box 452, Stellenbosch, 7599, South Africa. Tel. +27 21 8864496 (ask for Diedré Cloete), fax +27 21 8838177, email isrse@mikom.csir.co.za, <http://www.isrse.co.za/>

Abstract deadline: 30 July 1999.
Submissions can be made by email or at the WWW site.

Remote Sensing and Hydrology 2000. 2–7 April 2000, Santa Fe, New Mexico.

Ms. Laura O'Hare, USDA-ARS Hydrology Lab, Rm. 104, Bldg 007, BARC-W, Beltsville, MD 20705-2350, USA. <http://hydrolab.arsusda.gov/cf2k/conf2000.htm>

Tenth ASTM Symposium on Environmental Toxicology and Risk Assessment. 10–12 April 2000, Toronto, Canada.

B. Greenberg, Department of Biology, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada. Tel. +1 519 888 4567 ext. 3209, fax +1 519 746 0614, email greenber@sciborg.uwaterloo.ca

Abstract deadline is August 31 1999.

Eighth International Conference on Ground Penetrating Radar. 23–26 May 2000, Gold Coast, Queensland, Australia.

D. Noon, Department of Computer Science and Electrical Engineering, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia 4072. Tel +61 7 3365 3693, fax +61 7 3365 3684, email gpr2000@csee.uq.edu.au, <http://www.cssip.edu.au/Conferences/>

Abstract deadline is 5 November.

Event: DG XII supports radiation protection initiatives. 5–8 June 2000, Pisa, Italy.

The deadline for submitting abstract is 15 December 1999.

The workshop will:

- Review the state-of-the-art in neutron spectrometry;
- Report on recent developments and improvements;
- Demonstrate the many applications of neutron spectroscopy.

The workshop will include discussions on a number of topics. Some topics, such as 'workplace radiation from field analysis' and 'neutron diagnostics at plasma experiments', will be discussed in working groups.

For conference announcement, contact European Commission, DG XII — Science, Research and Development, Mrs C. A. Jackson, 200 rue de la Loi, B-1049 Brussels. Tel. +32-2-2960188; fax +32-2-2966256, email christine-ann.jackson@dg12.cec.be

For enquiries related to the scientific programme, please contact: Horst Klein, PTB, Dept 6.4 'Neutron Metrology', Bundesallee 100, D-38116 Braunschweig. Tel. +49-531-5926400; fax +49-531-5927205, email horst.klein@ptb.de <http://www.ptb.de/neuspec/start.htm>

ACCURACY 2000 — 4th International Symposium on Spatial Accuracy Assessment in Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences. July 12-14, 2000, De Rode Hoed, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

"Within the environmental sciences — whether it be hydrology, soil science, geomorphology, oceanography, forestry, climatology, geo-ecology or any other branch that one may think of — much use is made of spatially distributed data. These data, frequently stored as maps in a spatial data base or Geographical Information System (GIS), are rarely, if ever, truly free of error. Furthermore, these data are often used as inputs to various models of environmental processes that are themselves also subject to uncertainty. Spatial statistics and stochastic systems theory offer methodologies to handle these uncertainties, but the successful implementation and application of these methods requires the joint efforts of scientists from various disciplines.

The aim of this Symposium is to bring together experts from environmental science, spatial statistics and geographic information science to further develop theory and practical application of handling spatial uncertainty in the environmental sciences.

Building on the success of the previous symposia in Williamsburg, Virginia (1994), Fort Collins, Colorado (1996) and Quebec City, Canada (1998), this Symposium is the international meeting place for experts taking special interests in the assessment, modelling, visualisation and propagation of uncertainty in spatial data and spatial process models.

Topics of interest include:

- Development of error-sensitive GIS
- Theory and application of uncertainty propagation in spatial modelling
- Handling uncertainty in remotely sensed images and classification
- Design-based and model-based approaches to spatial uncertainty assessment
- Stochastic spatial simulation
- Handling spatio-temporal uncertainty
- Spatial uncertainty modelling for categorical data

- Visualisation of spatial uncertainty
- Effects of aggregation and generalisation on spatial uncertainty assessment
- Incorporating uncertainty in spatial decision making
- Inverse estimation techniques for calibrating spatial process models
- Simultaneous handling of positional and attribute uncertainty
- Discretisation and up-scaling effects for global environmental models
- Model validation with imperfect ground truth data"

1 October 1999: *Deadline for submission of extended abstracts*
15 March 2000: *Deadline for paper submission*
1 October 2000: *Deadline for submission to special issue of IJGIS*

Contact accuracy@frw.uva.nl or see <http://www.gis.wau.nl/Accuracy2000/>

Meteorology at the Millennium. 10–14 July 2000, Cambridge, UK.

A conference celebrating the 150th anniversary of the Royal Meteorological Society. It will explore developments in the atmospheric sciences and interactions with other branches of science and society. Leading international speakers will be present.

Executive Secretary, Royal Meteorological Society, 104 Oxford Road, Reading RG1 7LL, United Kingdom. Tel (0118) 9568500, fax (0118) 9568571, email execsec@royal-met-soc.org.uk, <http://itu.rdg.ac.uk/rms/conf2000/>

Abstract deadline: *31 December 1999.*

The Extremes of the Extremes: An International Symposium on Extraordinary Floods. 17–19 July 2000, Reykjavik, Iceland.

A. Snorrason, Director, Grensasvegur 9, IS-108 Reykjavik, Iceland. Tel. +354 569 6000, fax +354 568 8896, email asn@os.is, www.os.is/vatnam/extremes2000

Abstract deadline is 31 October.

International Association of Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth Interior (IAVCEI) General Assembly 2000. 18–23 July 2000, Bandung, Indonesia.

Theme is "Exploring volcanoes: utilisation of their resources and mitigation of their hazards".

Secretariat, Volcanological Survey of Indonesia, Jalan Diponegoro 57, Bandung 40122, Indonesia. Tel +62 22 772606, fax +62 22 702761, email iavcei@vsi.dpe.go.id, <http://www.vsi.dpe.go.id/iavcei.html>

Abstract deadline: *29 February 2000.*

European Aerosol Conference. 4–8 September 2000, Dublin, Ireland.

The Aerosol Society, PO Box 34, Portishead, Bristol, BS20 7FE. www.aerosol-soc.org.uk

Abstract deadline is 29 February 2000.

Funding and Other Opportunities.

Framework 5: Frequently Asked Questions.

If you do scientific research or development, you need to know about Framework 5. But the structure and terminology can be very confusing.

- "Why do we need a European research and technological development policy at all?"
- "Who can coordinate a project?"
- "What is a cluster?"
- "What is the structure of a proposal?"

These questions and many more are answered at:

<http://europa.eu.int/comm/dg12/faq.html>

The UK Research Office also provides information at:

<http://www.ukro.ac.uk/subs/fp5guide/contracts/contracts.htm>

British Council/Poland Joint Research Collaboration Programme — Science, Technology, Environment, Health, Social Sciences

The Polish-British Joint Research Collaboration Programme (JRP) is jointly financed and managed in Poland by the British Council and the State Committee for Scientific Research (KBN). Grants are offered as contributions towards travel and living costs

only. The programme currently supports 80 active links and applications are now being sought for 2000.

Closing date: 31 October 1999

For further details see the British Council at:

www.britcoun.org/poland/science/poljrjcp.htm

Or contact:

Dr. Andrew Murray, British Council, Al Jerozolimiskie 59 00-698 Warszawa, Poland.
Tel: +48 22 695 5900 Fax: +48 22 621 9955 E-mail: andrew.murray@britcoun.org.pl

Fellowships — Japan/UK

Closing date: 20 March and 20 September each year

The Royal Society invites applications for a prestigious new fellowship programme consisting of a four year package comprising two years research in Japan followed by two years research back in the UK (2+2).

The programme is open to UK researchers in the natural and applied sciences and is run in association with the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) and the Science and Technology Agency (STA). The fellowships are aimed at young postdoctoral scientists to enable them to spend a significant period of research in Japan, which may be viewed as critical to their career development, and offer funding for two years on their return to the UK.

The programme is flexible to allow 1+1 applications (one year in Japan plus one year back in the UK) if a candidate prefers. An award to go to Japan, without the return element, may also be applied for.

For further details and application guidelines, please contact:
The International Exchanges Section. Tel. 0171 451 2556,
email: japandkorea@royalsoc.ac.uk, quoting ref UKRO

Details of all society's national and international funding opportunities are available at: <http://www.royalsoc.ac.uk/>

Call — Scientific & Technological Options Assessment Unit (STOA).

STOA is a unit in the Directorate-General for Research of the European Parliament (EP), which carries out research for the Committees of the EP assessing policy

options in science and technology and related areas. It is currently updating its database of potential contractors. Research organisations and researchers are invited to send information about their field(s) of specialisation and recent work.

Those replying must have qualifications and experience in a discipline relevant to STOA's work, in:

- technology assessment
- science policy analysis
- research evaluation
- foresight studies
- natural sciences
- engineering
- mathematics
- philosophy, or
- relevant social sciences.

"There is no special form of application. Please send a brief statement about you/your organisation, mentioning field of expertise, qualifications and experience, as well as full contact details. This may be sent by mail, fax or email. The most convenient method for us is email, with your information contained in the body of the message."

"When we send out a Restricted Call for Tenders, a response is usually required within one calendar month. Being on the list of potential contractors means that the person/organisation concerned will be taken into account when lists for future Restricted Calls for Tender are being compiled. It does not guarantee inclusion on such a list, nor does it guarantee the award of a contract."

Expressions of interest should be sent to: Mr Dick Holdsworth, Head of Unit, STOA, Directorate-General for Research, European Parliament, SCH 4/82, L-2929 Luxembourg. Email: rholdsworth@europarl.eu.int

No closing date.

DG-XVII Energy Supported Programmes

These include the following specific programmes:

- ENERGIE (Framework V Energy Subprogramme),
- SYNERGY (international cooperation),
- ALTENER (renewable sources of energy),
- SAVE (energy efficiency),
- CARNOT (clean and efficient use of solid fuels), and
- THERMIE (Non-nuclear RTD)

- INTERREG II (Cross-Border Cooperation and Completion of Energy Networks)
- Trans-European Energy Networks
- The Euro-Mediterranean Energy Forum

See <http://www.europa.eu.int/en/comm/dg17/programs.htm>

A "Guide to Energy Efficiency Bankable Proposals" ...

... is also available at the above Web site, free of charge.

International Geological Correlation Programme

"The International Geological Correlation Programme (IGCP) is a co-operative enterprise of UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation) and IUGS (International Union of Geological Sciences). It was launched in 1972, to facilitate geological co-operation across international borders, as geological processes and structures normally cut across such boundaries. The programme's major aim was to bring together scientists from East and West and to encourage the involvement of developing countries.

IGCP is interdisciplinary, covering all specialities of the Earth Sciences and establishing links with other UNESCO scientific programmes. It maintains active interfaces with disciplines related to these such as marine, atmospheric and biological sciences. Its purpose is to promote the wise use of the Earth as a human habitat and as a source of natural resources. IGCP operates world-wide with several thousand of scientists in about 150 countries.

Reflecting the contemporary needs of society, the four main objectives of IGCP are as follows:

- (1) Increase our understanding of the factors controlling the global environment in order that human living conditions may be improved.
- (2) Develop more effective ways to find and assess natural resources of energy and minerals.
- (3) Increase knowledge of geological processes and geological concepts through correlative studies of many locations around the globe.
- (4) Improve standards of research, methods and techniques of carrying out research."

Applications may be made at any time.

For further details see the UNESCO website:

www.unesco.org/general/eng/programmes/science/programme/envIRON/igcp/index.html

Or contact: IGCP Secretariat, Division of Earth Sciences, UNESCO, 1 rue Miollis, F-75732 Paris Cedex 15. Email igcp@unesco.org

Call: British Council Spain Programme 1999-2000.

The British Council invites applications in all subject areas for inclusion in the 1999/2000 programme. This scheme is run jointly with the Spanish Ministry of Education and Culture in order to promote collaboration between groups from universities and public sector research institutes in both countries, through the award of travel and subsistence grants for joint research projects.

Applications must have already identified a Spanish project partner who should make a simultaneous application to the Spanish Ministry of Education and Culture. Application forms and further information may be obtained from:

Science Department, The British Council, Paseo General Martinez Campos, 31, 28010 Madrid, Spain. Tel: +34 91 337 3559/5031, fax: 00 34 91 337 3560. Email science@es.britcoun.org

European Commission Tender: establishment of a guide for the realistic assessment of radiation doses to members of the public due to operation of nuclear installations under normal conditions.

OJ S 136 (16/7/99), Document Number 101013-1999

Awarding authority: European Commission, DG-XI, Environment, Nuclear Safety and Civil Protection, Radiation protection unit (XI.C.1), rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Bruxelles/Brussel.

Award procedure: Open invitation to tender.

Subject of the contract: The Commission is awarding a contract to cover the establishment of a guide recommending methodologies for realistic radiation dose assessment to reference groups of the population resulting from normal operation of existing individual nuclear installations. The primary application of this guidance will be to retrospective assessments. The contract foresees commissioning of a document which enables any Member States' competent authority or regulatory body to undertake a realistic assessment of population doses.

Contract duration: 24 months from the date of signature.

Further information can be obtained from the European Commission, rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Brussels, for the attention of Mr B. Sinnott, DG-XI.3 (Market Team), marked reference C1/ETU/990058.

Deadline for request of documents: 2 September 1999
Deadline for submission: 17 September 1999

EC Tender: study on the current regulatory status in the EU Member States and the applicant countries concerning environmental impact assessments for the decommissioning of nuclear installations

OJ S 136 (16/7/99), Document Number 101012-1999

Awarding authority: European Commission, DG-XI, Environment, Nuclear Safety and Civil Protection, Nuclear safety, regulation and radioactive waste management unit, rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Bruxelles/Brussel.

Award procedure: Open invitation to tender (ref: C2/ETU/990060).

Subject of the contract: The Commission is awarding a study contract whose objectives are to cover:

The primary objective of the work would be to give an overview of the applicable laws and regulations in the Member States and the applicant countries. This should be completed by an extensive analysis of the national requirements as well as to what extent some national regulations are going further than the strict compliance with the EC directive. This will give the Commission services the opportunity to have a clearer understanding of how the EIA is formally used and if the directive is applied correctly. A second objective will be the drawing up of clear practical guidelines taking fully into account all the provisions laid down in both directives and the proposals described in the EC review check list (June 1994), and guides on screening and scoping methodology (May 1996) as far as it concerns the decommissioning of nuclear installations. It would examine in detail the role played by the EIA in the preparation of decommissioning plans.

The guidelines, being nuclear reactor oriented, will certainly focus on the particular design of the most frequent reactor type in the EU, the pressurized water reactor, but will also give useful indicators for graphite-gas reactors. Nevertheless, other parts of the nuclear fuel cycle should not be underestimated (e.g. enrichment and reprocessing facilities). The proposed EIA guidelines should be brought in line with the main decommissioning stages proposed by the International Atomic Energy Agency.

Adopting a range of required analysis and evaluation processes would have implications for the degree of sophistication of an EIA and hence on the effort

required to prepare it and on the cost. These implications would also need to be evaluated.

While preparation of an EIA can involve considerable time and effort, it can also be used as a communication tool with the public. The role played by the public, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and consumer groups in the preparation and evaluation of an EIA may vary from 1 Member State to another. The guidelines will suggest, if necessary, how it might be enhanced.

Contract duration: 15 months from the date of signature.

Documents (technical annex) can be obtained from the European Commission, rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B-1049 Bruxelles/Brussel, for the attention of Mr B.Sinnott, DG-XI.3 (Market Team) marked reference C2/ETU/990060, tel. (32-2) 296 00 08 (administrative and financial matters) /296 38 82 (technical matters), by letter or facsimile (32-2) 299 44 49

Request for documents deadline: 6 September 1999
Submission deadline: 21 September 1999

EC Tender: study on on-board diagnostic systems for emission control of motor vehicles (OBD)

OJ S 134 (14/7/99), Document Number 85745-1999
Call for tender No. III/99/025

Contracting authority: The European Community, represented by the European Commission, Directorate-General-III, Industry, Unit (E5), Mrs V. Groebner (Head of Unit), office AN 88: 2/53, rue de la Loi/Wetstraat 200, B1049 Bruxelles/Brussel. Tel. (32-2) 299 00 78. Facsimile (32-2) 296 96 37.

Category of service and description: Study concerning on-board diagnostic systems for emission control of motor vehicles (OBD); the study will assess the need, or otherwise, to lower OBD threshold limit values and feasibility of extending or modifying the application of OBD in relation to such aspects as historical vehicle performance, use of alternative fuels, standard electronic function for repair information and heavy duty vehicle. Central product classification: CPC 865/866.

Time limits for starting, delivery or completion or duration of service contract: Work is projected to commence in November 1999 and to be of 12 months duration.

Contact: Contracting authority (see above)

Deadline for request of documents: 31 August 1999
Deadline for receipt: 6 September 1999

European Call: Altener II Call for proposals for actions related to the promotion of renewable energy sources in the European Community

OJ C 187 (03.07.99) pp.19-20
Closing date: 30 November 1999

Altener is the non-technology programme for the promotion of renewable energies in the European Union.

Proposals are sought for the following actions and measures:

Studies and other actions intended to implement and complement Community and Member States' measures aimed at developing the potential of renewable energy sources. These include the development of sector and market strategies, the development of norms and certifications, comparative analyses of the environmental impact and the long term cost/benefit trends resulting from the use of traditional forms of energy and the use of renewable energy sources, and the analyses of the legal, socio-economic and administrative conditions which are more favourable to the penetration of renewable energies and the preparation of appropriate legislation.

Promotion and dissemination measures to develop information, education and training structures, to encourage the exchange of experience and know-how aimed at improving coordination between international, Community, national, regional and local activities; establishment of a centralised system for collecting, prioritising and circulating information and know-how on renewable energy sources.

[... and much more ...]

An information package setting out all details for submission will be sent on written request. European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy, Mr. Harbison, DG XVII/C-2 TERV A-1/24, Rue de la Loi 200, B-1049 Brussels.
Fax +32 2 296 62 83, email altener@bxl.dg17.cec.be
<http://europa.eu.int/en/comm/dg17/altener.htm>

DG-XI (Environment): Consultation on Integrated Coastal Zone Management

DG XI has produced a strategy document on 'Towards a European Integrated Coastal Zone Management Strategy'. It is comprised of 2 documents, one of which examines the general principles and policy options and the other examines lessons learned from the Commission's demonstration programme in this area. In the appendix to the policy document, individuals and organisations are invited to send written comments on the document.

The deadline for comments is 30 September 1999.

To obtain the documents contact: Anne Burrill at DG XI-D-2, European Commission, rue de la Loi 200, 1049 Brussels, email anne.burrill@dg11.cec.be

NERC Data Assimilation Thematic Programme — Calls for Proposals

The NERC Earth Observation Expert Group invites proposals under its Data Assimilation thematic research programme. This programme is directed at research which uses data assimilation techniques to derive maximum value from remotely sensed atmospheric and oceanographic data gathered by national, European and international agencies, and which helps to develop the expertise of the UK scientific community in this area.

The primary objectives of the programme are:

- To improve data assimilation techniques and to apply these techniques to combine new types of remotely-sensed observations with conventional atmospheric and/or oceanic data.
- To use data assimilation techniques to make efficient and effective use of remotely-sensed data in support of national, European and international programmes in earth observation.
- To build comprehensive three-dimensional global data sets of the evolving state of the atmosphere and oceans for dissemination to the user community, and to provide archiving facilities and visualisation software.
- To provide first-class interdisciplinary training in earth observation sciences, mathematical techniques and numerical modelling.

Proposals are invited from individuals and groups of scientists at UK universities and government research establishments who wish to apply for funding for the development of methods of data assimilation, the production of assimilated data sets or the establishment of infrastructure for the production of assimilated data from future observational programmes.

Closing date: 15 September 1999

See <http://www.soc.soton.ac.uk/PR/DataAssAO.html>

Or contact: Programme Manager, Ms Anne I Morrison Rm254/35 James Rennell Division Southampton Oceanography Centre European Way Southampton SO14 3ZH. Email Anne.I.Morrison@soc.soton.ac.uk

EUMETSAT: Invitations to tender on-line.

As of 1 January 1999, EUMETSAT presents its Invitations to Tender entirely on the WWW. See <http://www.eumetsat.de/eumits>

The Blasker Award for Environmental Science and Engineering.

Quoted from the announcement:

"It is with great pleasure that we write to tell you about an innovative \$250,000 award and encourage you to either submit an application, nominate someone, or share with this information with colleagues, students and others whose work you think would be a strong candidate for the award.

In the year 2001, the third Blasker Award for Environmental Science and Engineering will be given for novel science and technology achievements contributing toward renewal of land to make possible its sustainable, beneficial use. Examples of eligible areas include land reclamation, remediation of brown fields and soil contamination, and the facilitation of reforestation. Applications will be accepted until **October 15, 2000**.

Other topics for which we are accepting applications are: [... deadline passed ...]; and contributions to environmentally sustainable supplies of energy, deadline **October 15, 1999**."

Application forms are available from blasker@sdfoundation.org, fax +1 619 239 1710, www.blasker.org

Publications and General Information

GCOS Electronic Newsletter (Global Climate Observing System)

The new version will be a bi-monthly electronic newsletter called GCOS E-News.

This newsletter will reports activities of the GCOS Joint Scientific and Technical Committee (JSTC), the Joint Planning Office (JPO), and national and international activities related to GCOS. It will be prepared by the GCOS JPO.

Interested persons can subscribe to GCOS E-News by sending an e-mail message to: gcoss_newsletter@gateway.wmo.ch

The subject line should contain the following: Subscribe GCOS E-News

Marine research project synopses

Extended summaries of marine research projects, published by DG XII. The following are covered:

1. Marine systems research covering extreme marine environments and regional seas research;
2. Strategic marine research covering coastal and shelf seas, coastal engineering and natural defences;
3. Generic technologies;
4. Advanced systems.

To obtain copies of the volumes of project synopses, please contact: European Commission, DG XII — Science, research and development, MAST programme — Unit D/3, 200 rue de la Loi, B-1049 Brussels. Email: mast-info@dg12.ccc.be
<http://europa.eu.int/comm/dg12/envsc/events.html>

EEA Report on Urban Air Quality in Europe

"Assessment and Management of Urban Air Quality in Europe."
European Environment Agency
ISBN 92-9167-103-7

Obtainable from: Office for Official Publication of the European Communities, L-2985 Luxembourg.

DG XI new web site on environmental emergencies: civil protection and accidental marine pollution.

<http://europa.eu.int/comm/dg11/civil/index.htm>

European Environment Agency Reports

Various reports are available free in Adobe PDF format at www.eea.eu.int/frdocu.htm including:

- Environment in the European Union at the turn of the century.
- Europe's Environment: the Second Assessment

- Environment in European Union 1995: Report for the Review of the Fifth Environmental Action Programme

Quoted with permission from the summary document of "Environment in the European Union at the turn of the century":

The Agency has previously reported that despite more than 25 years of Community Environmental Policy – which has been successful in its own terms – general environmental quality in the EU is not recovering significantly, and in some areas, it is worsening. This present report confirms both that situation and the fact that the unsustainable development of some economic sectors is the major barrier to improvement.

Up to now what has been missing has been an assessment of whether the actual economic, sectoral and environmental policies over the next decade or so will bring improvements, or whether there are trends and developments pushing us off target and seriously challenging substantial progress.

This report, 'Environment in the European Union at the turn of the century' is designed to address this issue and provide information on current state and future trends of direct use for deciding on sound and effective measures to really improve and protect the environment, and to move towards more sustainable development (Amsterdam Treaty, Articles 2 and 6).

What do we see?

In summary, most of the major challenges will continue over the next decade, namely significant societal developments (in GDP, population, consumption) and, despite some notable exceptions, a general failure to de-link these from environmental pressures; increasing environmental burdens from the growth of road and air transport, and general urbanisation and 'suburbanisation'; degradation of the rural environment; and increasingly significant risks to the valuable natural and biodiversity assets of central and eastern European countries, as well to those remaining in southern and Mediterranean countries and in northern and western Europe.

But also we see some still small but fast-growing positive signals that should be known about more widely, disseminated and encouraged: growth in wind energy; cycling taking higher percentages of some cities' traffic; pesticide-free areas or municipalities being declared in many countries; a significant growth in organic agriculture; improving energy efficiency in many countries; some EU countries establishing indicators and even quantitative targets to master unsustainable development; and many municipalities and companies embracing sustainability as a feasible and profitable process developing their own local Agenda 21 programmes at local and business level.

What else do we need to identify and report on that could help in improving environmental quality and overcoming unsustainable trends?

As the Agency has struggled to build a seamless monitoring and reporting system, what has been missing is a more structured reference model with indicators and eventually targets for the main issues. In short, we have not had the instruments to make the socio-economic system accountable, in environmental and sustainability terms, to encourage and reward it to take a sustainable path.

The Agency will now move a further step forward by implementing the new obligation (Review of the 1210/1990 Council Regulation) to issue regular reports

based on indicators. The first report to be published to provide a set of EU Environment Signals, by the end of 1999, will present an extended package of indicators to show progress and trends. From this a set of so-called 'headline indicators' will be identified. Together with GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and other key welfare indicators, attempts are being made to produce a so-called 'well-being index' beyond GDP, to better represent quality of life including environmental quality and progress with sustainability.

Since all this implies change, the political framework is also important. Environmental policy may have eased some problems, but economic and sectoral policies beyond the control of environmental policy have created new and bigger ones. The integration of environment into other policies is destined to face conflict. However, the 'Cardiff Initiative' (European Council of June 1998), has begun to operationalise this by calling upon the key economic and sectoral policies (Agriculture, Transport, Energy, Internal Market, Industry, Finance, Development) to be accountable in environmental and sustainability terms. The Helsinki Council in December 1999 should take stock of progress and link these sectoral developments with a Global Assessment of the Fifth Environmental Action programme (to which this report is an input). A coordinated report on indicators (to which the EEA 1999 Environmental signals report is a main contribution) is also to be presented by the European Commission.

The present report is one step on the way to more effective reporting. The approach taken here is expected to allow for more successful partnerships tackling environment and sustainability issues; partnerships involving policy makers, users and consumers, the ordinary citizen, and not least of all, business and industry, which now understands that there will be no business if it is not sustainable business. Such developments are part of the move from 'environment as a burden' to 'environment and as an opportunity'. Forthcoming reports, and in particular our yearly 'EU Environmental signals' report based on indicators, should allow a more frequent monitoring of progress than our three or five-yearly report have hitherto allowed. These reports will also be the opportunity to identify, and perhaps even to focus upon, emerging positive experiences and trends, including indicators on encouraging issues or topics, disaggregated spatial (by Member States) or sectorally.

Both the reporting and accountability frameworks seem to be improving as do the political will, the readiness of the business sector and the public demands and expectations. We have two big challenges in front of us that could become increasing opportunities for ultimately testing our will and our capacities to improve the environment and quality of life quality and progress towards sustainable development: The climate change challenge or the reduction of greenhouse gases or rational use of fossil fuels (from climate change to a climate for change) and the enlargement of the EU (taking sustainability as a goal and compliance as a result). Let us do it.

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Executive Director

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Report on ATLAS — New Energy Technologies

The ATLAS Project was a major strategic review exercise aimed at identifying key issues and guiding priorities for the next phase of EU support programmes and other actions in the field of new energy technologies.

This study was funded under the former EU programme 'THERMIE', the non-nuclear energy technology demonstration and dissemination component of the 4th Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development. During 1996 and 1997 the study, carried out by members of the European network of energy agencies (EnR), gathered extensive data on all the latest energy technologies, their current and future market status, the RTD needs, and their importance to EU energy policy relevant to the whole non-nuclear energy field, with the exception of oil and gas, to a time horizon extending to the year 2010.

For each of 50 selected energy technologies in the broad sectors of Rational Use of Energy, Renewable Energy Sources and Heat & Power Generation, it has considered:

- Current usage
- Potential future usage
- Market barriers to increased development
- Competitiveness in a world wide context
- Environmental sustainability
- Technical Developments required.

This website provides a comprehensive review of the work done in an easy searchable format. The information presented is intended to provide advice to RTD decision makers at all levels on the priorities and directions for future programmes.

<http://europa.eu.int/en/comm/dg17/atlas/atlas-hp.htm>

ESA Launches "Living Planet" Programme June 7 1999

From the press release:

The Living Planet Programme is the most comprehensive Earth observation programme ever to be launched. It received the go-ahead at ESA's Ministerial Council meeting in Brussels on 12 May. Compared with present expenditure, the Programme will cut Earth observation costs by more than 25%, as it calls upon private funding of research and development to complement public investment.

Most Living Planet projects will greatly deepen scientific knowledge of how the Earth works. Over the forthcoming years, each Living Planet project will

contribute to continuous, accurate environmental monitoring of our planet, of its climate and of global change.

More information on ESA can be found at <http://www.esa.int>

Blue Book on Geothermal Resources

Executive summary:

Geothermal energy is one of the indigenous and environmentally friendly energy resources in use which the European Union intends to expand in order to reach its established goals for RE contribution to gross energy consumption in Europe, from the present 6% to 12% by the year 2010.

A key aim of the Blue book is to identify a series of measures which could effectively promote the use of geothermal energy in the EU, EEA countries and Switzerland, as well as countries that are likely to become associated with the EU in the near future (Agenda 2000 countries).

This study describes the present world-wide status of geothermal development, and the availability of geothermal resources. The advantages and benefits that make geothermal energy competitive, environmentally beneficial, reliable and safe compared to most other energy sources are also presented.

A detailed analysis of the global market conditions is also presented with short term opportunities and medium term development prospects by 2010. Furthermore, the Blue Book identifies a series of actions to develop the geothermal sector in the EU, particularly measures to increase the presence of European operators in the domestic and world geothermal markets.

12 pages, available free of charge in Adobe PDF format at:

<http://www.europa.eu.int/en/comm/dg17/altener.htm>

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